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THE ROLE OF INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN MANAGING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF ENTERPRISES IN WORLD MARKETS

РОЛЬ ІННОВАЦІЙНОГО МЕНЕДЖМЕНТУ В УПРАВЛІННІ КОНКУРЕНТОСПРОМОЖНІСТЮ ПІДПРИЄМСТВ НА СВІТОВИХ РИНКАХ

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Леоненко К.Р., Ляшевська В.І., Носова О.В. Роль інноваційного менеджменту в управлінні конкурентоспроможністю підприємств на світових ринках. Оглядова стаття.

У статті розглянуто інноваційний менеджмент як ключовий фактор формування конкурентоспроможності галузей і підприємств на світових ринках. Проаналізовано сутність понять: інновація, інноваційна діяльність та конкурентоспроможність. Визначено структуру інноваційного потенціалу та його взаємозв'язок з іншими потенціалами господарюючого суб'єкта. За критерієм інноваційного розвитку було розглянуто і досліджено проблеми управління конкурентоспроможністю підприємства. Визначено особливості процесів, що виникають, на підставі запропонованої моделі формування та реалізації інноваційного потенціалу підприємства, а також його трансформації в інноваційний капітал. Обумовлено принципи управління конкурентоспроможністю підприємства. Доведено відповідність принципам методу управління конкурентоспроможністю на основі економіки знань.

Ключові слова: конкурентоспроможність, управління, інновації, інноваційний менеджмент, інноваційний потенціал, інноваційний капітал

Leonenko K.R., Liashevska V.I., Nosova O.V. The role of innovation management in managing the competitiveness of enterprises in world markets. Review article.

The article examines innovation management as a key factor in the formation of the competitiveness of industries and enterprises in world markets. The essence of the concepts is analyzed: innovation, innovative activity and competitiveness. The structure of innovation potential and its interrelation with other potentials of the economic entity are determined. For the criterion of innovative development, the problems of managing the competitiveness of an enterprise were considered and investigated. The features of the processes arising on the basis of the proposed model for the formation and implementation of the innovative potential of an enterprise, as well as its transformation into innovative capital, are indicated. The principles of enterprise competitiveness management have been determined. Compliance with the principles of the competitiveness management method based on the knowledge economy has been proved.

Keywords: competitiveness, management, innovation, innovation management, innovation potential, innovation capital

The key task of the world economy is the innovative renewal of used technologies and products. This is the basis of economic growth, meeting the ever-growing needs of the population in a variety of quality goods and services. In these conditions, all enterprises and all business entities should be engaged in innovation management. Innovative activity provides them with competitive advantages, strengthens and expands their market position [4, p.63].

The transition of the country's economy to an innovative path of development determines the dynamics of economic growth and the level of competitiveness of enterprises within industries and in the world economy. Therefore, enterprises of all industries face the same problems: in the context of globalization, which covers new areas of activity, competition is intensifying not only nationally but also in world markets. Therefore, domestic companies have to increasingly compete for quality and technical level of products with foreign companies, which in turn have certain advantages. In order for companies to be able to compete with foreign companies, it is necessary to have competitive production, accompanied by high quality products and low costs.

One of the factors that can increase the competitiveness of enterprises is the factor of innovative development, which involves the interdependent formation of scientific and technical, industrial, financial, social activities in a new institutional environment. An important aspect of enterprises is not in the choice of certain areas of innovation management, but in understanding the

conceptual and methodological approaches to building assessments of the impact of innovative developments and products on the competitiveness of firms to build effective innovation policy. Regardless of the position of the company, its market share, its size, its organizational and legal status, the vast majority of innovations will increase profits by optimizing production, management system and process facilitation of production.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The study of the role of innovation management is devoted to the study of domestic and foreign economists. We highlight in particular the works of V.P. Alexandrova, B.M. Geetsya, G.I. Kalytycha, O.A. Lapko, A.I. Sukhorukova, A.I. Yakovlev and others. The problem of managing the competitiveness of the enterprise, given the significant impact and role of innovation management is relevant today for world countries, as evidenced by the works of well-known foreign scholars, including M. Porter (Porter, 2001), B. Santo (Santo, 1990), R. Solow (Solow, 1962), H. Freeman (Freeman, 2002), J. Schumpeter (Schumpeter, 1995) and other authors. However, given the lack of justification of existing aspects of the problem, such as conditions of market uncertainty, the presence of which is characteristic of the activities of enterprises in the modern economy, we consider it appropriate to more fully cover the research issue. At the same time, the impact of innovation on the degree of competitiveness of enterprises in world markets requires detailed study.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

Today, the development of the world economy, including the Ukrainian economy, directly depends on competition and the impact of innovation on the scale of economic growth. Increasing use of innovations on a large scale is associated with increasing levels of economic development [2]. At the moment, any intellectual work is paid higher than other types of work.

The modern world market puts its conditions in connection with increasing competition in order to use innovations and innovations, increase innovation activity. It is important for any company to have stability in the market and have an advantage over its competitors, and that is why it is forced to look for new systems to organize their business.

One of the factors that can increase the competitiveness of business in world markets is the active use of innovation management, which will lead to the formation of scientific and technical, industrial, financial, social activities in a new institutional environment [1].

The management system of innovation activity of the enterprise is one of the local management systems at the enterprise. Therefore, in order to achieve the desired results and defined goals, it is necessary that the innovation management system functions in harmony with other local management subsystems.

The aim of the article is to determine the features of innovation management, analysis of the problems of managing the competitiveness of the enterprise on the

criticism of innovative development, providing recommendations for improving the competitiveness of enterprises in world markets.

The main part

The current state of the market can be described by the constant change of the external environment, the variability of consumer demand, the presence of a large number of enterprises of various forms of ownership, increased uncertainty and risk. Therefore, in order to survive, companies need to constantly monitor and respond to all changes in their competitive environment in order to maintain their market position and ensure competitive advantage. For each company today, an important task is to accurately assess the market situation to offer effective means of competition, which, on the one hand, would meet market conditions in Ukraine and its development trends, and on the other hand, the specifics of the company [5, p.77-78].

M. Porter in his works carried out a detailed analysis of competitive advantages. The scientist suggested that national prosperity is not inherited, is not a consequence of available natural resources or labor, but is formed. Competitiveness depends on the ability of enterprises to innovate and modernize. The maintenance of competitive advantages becomes possible due to the constant improvement of products, means of production and all other factors. Thus, the basis of competitive advantage is the process of continuous stimulation of renewal and improvement [1, p.92-93]. In this case, do not do without innovation. It is necessary to characterize this concept.

For the most part, the term "innovation" can be found in the economic literature. This term should be understood as the transformation of potential scientific and technological progress into a real result of its activities by introducing it into new products, products and technologies.

Innovations, changes, innovations – these terms began to be widely used both independently and to describe related concepts: innovation, innovation process, innovation management, innovation management, innovation solution and more.

It is known that there are many definitions of these concepts and interpretations of these categories in the literature.

So, the first was the Austrian scientist I. Schumpeter, who formulated the definition of innovation in the early twentieth century. He defined them as a new scientific and organizational combination of factors of production, which is motivated by entrepreneurial spirit [3, p.441].

American scientist F. Nixon noted that innovation is a combination of technical, production and commercial activities, which leads to the emergence of new and improved industrial processes and equipment [3, p.442].

In the general sense of the essence of innovation processes occurring in any complex production and economic system, it is a set of progressive, qualitatively new changes that continuously occur in time and space, as well as contribute to the further

quality of society. standard of living, it is a consistent system of measures, as a result of which innovations are transformed from an idea into a specific product, technology, structure or service and spread in economic practice and social activities [7, p.121].

There are five main types of innovation in modern economic theory, namely:

- services (market innovation);
- development of a new source of raw materials and semi-finished products (marketing innovation);
- reorganization of the management structure (managerial innovation).

Innovation management – one of those areas of strategic management, which is carried out at the highest level of the organization [4, p.80]. Its purpose

is to establish key areas of scientific, technical and production activities of the organization. First of all, it is the development and implementation of new products and technologies (innovation), modernization and improvement of products and technologies, further development of traditional products and departure from the production of obsolete products.

As well as any other sphere of management for innovation management are characteristic:

- goal setting and strategy selection;
- four stages of the cycle: planning, setting conditions and organization, implementation, leadership.

At the fig. 1 we present the main characteristics of innovation management.

Figure 1. Scheme of innovation management
Source: compiled by authors on materials [4-5].

Mastering the mechanism of managing innovation processes is a prerequisite for making radical decisions in the economic, political and social life of our country as a whole. The tasks of innovation management are to solve the problems of organizations in adapting them to new economic conditions, to the changes that are constantly occurring in their environment in order to achieve economic growth.

Compatibility and synergy means the ability of the innovation management system and other systems in the organization to complement each other, the ability to adapt, not to conflict, not to create conflicts, to adapt to achieve the best end result [9].

The task of innovation management is effective management of the process of development, implementation, production and commercialization of innovations with the coordination of relevant solutions with management systems of operational (production), marketing, financial and human resources [6, p.11].

The direction of innovation is determined primarily by the creation of production of new goods and services. In the global market, the company will be considered successful if it is engaged in innovation. After all, it is innovation that requires high costs, but at the same time is a source of income. Planning and

managing innovation is an important and complex process, as the individuality of the business environment and the dynamics of its changes are constantly growing. Innovations that affect the competitiveness of global enterprises are classified as follows:

- by the nature of relations: socio-economic, organizational, technological innovations;
- by scope: production, management, technical and social innovations;
- by subject-content structure: product, process and allocation innovations [8].

Thanks to this classification, we can identify the main areas of influence of innovation management on the management of competitiveness of global enterprises (Table. 1).

Considering the main types of innovation should point to the general factors of innovation potential of the enterprise.

To a greater extent, the conditions for the formation of innovation potential are created by factors of the internal environment of the enterprise, and the conditions for its implementation - external. Of course, in reality these factors are inextricably linked, and some of them are interdependent.

Table 1. Areas of influence of innovation management on managing the competitiveness of global enterprises

Types of innovations	Impact on competitiveness
Socio-economic	Optimize the use of resources, such as financial, to increase comparative and competitive advantages.
Management	Implementation of creative ideas in order to develop and create new methods and forms of management. In this regard, there is a restructuring of the management system, which leads to profits and competitiveness.
Technical	Use new technology to reduce costs.
Social	Improving working conditions, conducting trainings and other measures to increase employee motivation. The quality of the workforce determines the ability of the economic entity to carry out its own research and development (R&D) or copy new products from other firm [1].
Product	Improving the consumer properties of the product and increasing competitive advantage.
Process	Transformations made to the processes taking place in the enterprise will lead to lower costs, cost, quality, comparative and competitive advantages.
Allocation	Reorganization of the enterprise aimed at increasing competitiveness.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [6].

We highlight in particular that the formation of the innovative potential of the enterprise involves, above all, obtaining answers to the following questions:

- What to promote on the market?
- What innovative product should the company develop?
- How should the production of this product be organized, including which technological policy should be chosen?
- Who should deal with the problem of developing and implementing innovations?
- From what sources should this work be funded?

In our view, the factors shaping the innovation model can be logically represented as a set of key enterprise management systems, in essence, and aimed at obtaining answers to the above questions: marketing management, production management, personnel management and financial management. The challenge is to make each of these systems innovative. In other words, each of the main enterprise management systems must be appropriately tuned to the formation of an innovative model of development. This model can be described by four components: interest, sources, tools, information.

Interest. Adjusting management systems to form an innovative model of development in the first place, requires interest in the development of innovation from both owners and managers.

Sources. The next mandatory factor in creating conditions for the formation of innovative potential of the enterprise is the availability of sources of necessary resources: financial, material and intellectual. Today, it is difficult to determine which of these sources are decisive, but the special importance of intellectual resources should be emphasized.

Tools. Another factor is the development of a set of tools by the staff of the enterprise, which allows to carry out the full range of work on the development, production and promotion of an innovative product. Note that here the term "tool" is used in a broad sense. This term includes all the basic elements of the management system.

Information. Today, the information component is beginning to dominate in any business and plays such a significant role in its development that it seems

correct to allocate information in a separate factor from the composition of other resources [2].

Now let's briefly dwell on the conditions of realization of innovation potential. The analysis showed that the vector of development of competition theory is aimed at the growth of the intellectual component in establishing a stable competitive advantage [1, p.94]. This means that in modern conditions, the main source of prosperity and wealth of world economies are systematic and unique knowledge.

In most developed countries of the world today, competitive advantage, according to various estimates, from 67 to 97% is achieved through knowledge, skills and creative decisions [1, p.95]. The system of knowledge-based economy includes those that interact closely in a particular environment created by the market and the state, elements such as information and communication technologies, human capital, business, institutional environment and national innovation policy [3].

Thus, we consider it appropriate to propose the following model of formation and implementation of innovation potential with its further transformation into intellectual capital in order to increase the competitiveness of the enterprise (Fig. 2).

The model offered by us gives the chance to estimate innovative potential of the enterprise as set of estimations of the created conditions of its formation (factors of internal environment) and conditions of realization (factors of external environment).

The state of the factors of the internal environment is proposed to be determined using indicators that assess each of the four "components" of innovation management in terms of functional areas of management. Given that the evaluation indicators have different units of measurement, it is advisable to measure them on a point system, using expert methods. From our point of view, an integrated assessment of the state of these indicators can be used to characterize the degree of innovation activity of the enterprise.

The assessment of environmental factors as a condition for the realization of the innovative potential of the enterprise is proposed to be determined according to the following scheme.

Figure 2. Model of innovative development of the enterprise

Source: compiled by authors on materials [6].

First, you need to make a list of opportunities in the environment that the company needs to take advantage of. Second, with the help of experts to assess the likelihood of realizing these opportunities. And finally, thirdly, translate the last score into the scoring system in the range from -5 to +5 points.

It is proposed to assess the innovative potential of the enterprise as the ratio of actual assessments of the state of its internal and external environment to the maximum possible. The most optimal state in terms of formation and implementation of the innovative potential of the enterprise should be as close as possible to the diagonal separating the areas of "Accelerated Development" and "Lost Opportunities". This state will allow the company to transform its innovation potential into innovation capital and, ultimately, significantly increase the level of competitiveness.

The proposed method of calculating the innovation potential of the enterprise is based on the calculation of a consolidated, aggregate indicator that reflects the degree of impact on the innovation environment of the enterprise of each of the 4 groups of factors and is calculated by the following formula:

$$P_{innovation} = \frac{K_S * K_O}{K_W * K_T} \quad (1)$$

where K_S is the coefficient that reflects the influence of strengths;

K_O – a factor that reflects the impact of opportunities;

K_W – coefficient that reflects the influence of weaknesses;

K_T – a factor that reflects the impact of threats.

The consolidated indicator reflects the degree of favorable innovation activity of the enterprise, assessed now (how much and how many times the influence of positive factors is greater than the influence of negative factors).

Assuming some assumptions that allow us to estimate the threshold values of the coefficient of innovation potential of the enterprise (Pinnovac), we accept the following gradation:

- 0...0.3 – innovation potential is extremely low;
- 0.3...0.6 – innovation potential is low;
- 0.6...1.0 – innovation potential is relatively low;
- ...2.0 – innovation potential is high;
- ...10.0 – innovation potential is very high;
- 10.0 and above – the innovation potential is extremely high.

The effectiveness of innovation management of the enterprise, especially in world markets, in fact, reflects the degree of transformation of its innovation potential into innovation capital ($K_{in. cap.}$). The main difficulty of its assessment is the fact that different types of innovation can bring different results: the use of some leads to results in the short term, while others create opportunities for results in the long term. The most adequate assessment of such different results over time is the current net cash flow [10, p.27].

As you know, net cash flow is calculated as the difference between cash inflows and outflows for all activities of the enterprise: basic, investment and financial, in this case, all these activities should be

taken into account in terms of cash inflows and outflows related to development, production, implementation of innovations:

$$K_{in\ cap} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^t DCF_i}{P_{innovation}} \quad (2)$$

where DCF_i is the discounted cash flow as the difference between the discounted inflows and the discounted cash outflows over a period of time t ;

t – forecasting period;

i – forecasting step.

As a discount rate, it is logical to take the value of the weighted average cost of capital of the enterprise (WACC).

Research of the developed model allows to allocate the basic features of management of competitiveness of the enterprise from a position of formation and realization of its innovative potential and to form the corresponding principles of management according to which the adequate method of management should be chosen.

It is clear that the management of competitiveness, in principle, like any management, should be subject to a single goal, and this goal should be built into the overall system of objectives of the enterprise. Setting goals to achieve a given level of competitiveness of the enterprise should be subordinated to the principle of SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, timebound) proposed by P. Drucker. The staging must be concrete, computational, achievable, relevant and measurable over time. This allows us to formulate the first principle of competitiveness management – the principle of purposefulness and unity of purpose [7, p.122].

The most important feature of competitiveness management is the need to cover a large number of factors, both internal and external environment of the enterprise. It should be borne in mind that these factors are interrelated, differ, first, both positive and negative interactions of varying degrees; secondly, both positive and negative effects of varying degrees on the ultimate goal of management. Hence the second principle should be the principle of multifactorial and multiplicity of relations. Note that this principle, including, includes the principle of feedback.

The next feature of management is due to the complexity of the categories of enterprise and competitiveness and, accordingly, the characteristics of the system, formulated, in particular, in this study [11, p.46]:

- the behavior of each element of the system affects the behavior of the whole;
- each element affects the whole not independently, but in interaction with at least one other element;
- the system does not have such subgroups of elements that would affect the whole independently of other elements, it does not have full autonomy;
- the system is a whole that cannot be divided into independent parts; if the parts are separated from the system, they lose some of their properties;
- the system has properties that are missing in its part.

This correspondence allows us to formulate a third principle – the principle of systematization, the

implementation of which in the management of enterprise competitiveness will use all the benefits of a systematic approach, including synergetic effect, the possibility of which is due to bifurcation dynamics of innovation processes.

Another feature is the fact that the system of managing the competitiveness of the enterprise has a dual nature. The structure of control actions should change in accordance with changes in the parameters of the control object. This principle allows to achieve the adaptability of the management system. Adaptation in cybernetics is the accumulation and use of information to achieve in some sense the optimal state or behavior of the system with the initial uncertainty in external conditions. Adaptive is considered to be a system that can adapt to changes in internal and external conditions [2].

Along with the concept of adaptive system, there is the concept of adaptive management (adaptive management). Management in a system with incomplete a priori information about the managed process, which changes as information accumulates and is used to improve the quality of the system. Thus, the fourth principle of management – the principle of dual management or the principle of adaptability.

It is known that the classification of innovations distinguishes between innovation-products and innovation-processes, including management processes, and the focus on innovation, in principle, implies the use of innovative management technologies. However, it should be emphasized that innovative products can be created or borrowed faster through innovative management methods.

Another feature of competitiveness management is related to the very nature of competitiveness, namely the development of competition theory and dynamically changing competitive advantages over time. Rapidly changing environmental conditions, the monitoring of which provides feedback, should lead to adjustments or changes in both individual elements and the management system of competitiveness of the enterprise as a whole [8]. Hence the next principle – the principle of dynamism.

An important feature of competitiveness management according to the criterion of innovative development is the need to use knowledge. World experience and economic research in recent years show that knowledge is becoming a more important factor in economic development than traditional factors - labor and capital. The knowledge economy, as a new type of economy, is considered at three levels: macro-, meso- and microeconomics. It is clear that all of them are inextricably linked and interdependent, and the growth of competitiveness of a single business entity is determined by the interaction of all three levels. Thus, the last principle of management should be the principle of knowledge-based economy.

Conclusions

Summing up, we note that in an enterprise that carries out innovative activities, a necessary condition is the constant evaluation of the management system of these activities in order to avoid unplanned costs. It is

also important to evaluate this system in conjunction with other management systems. That is, it is necessary to assess the impact of costs and their feasibility on the functioning of each system. Carrying out comprehensive monitoring of existing systems at the enterprise will ensure its efficient operation and strong competitive position in world markets.

It is determined that the company should not be afraid of new changes, management should be prepared for innovations, as well as train staff for this. Business leaders should discuss with their subordinates the measures that will take place and give clear tasks to be solved. Therefore, the study of this process, namely how the new innovation will affect the production process is one of the main issues. Based on the above, it was justified the need to introduce innovation management in the enterprise management system, which provides new opportunities to achieve high results and reduce costs, as well as take new positions in the market.

It should be noted that the innovation process is a complex process that needs to be clearly analyzed and predicted, taking into account the risks and problems that may arise. Therefore, for the successful implementation of innovation, the organization must create an atmosphere of creativity, stimulating the search for new ideas; identify priority areas for innovative change; analyze the market in detail.

Harmonious and coordinated work of all enterprise systems, which act as components of one system, ensures the organization to achieve certain goals. The nature of the innovation management system of such properties as integrity, adaptability, development, compatibility and synergy allows for coordinated interaction with other management systems in the enterprise. During the operation of systems and their interaction, it is important to monitor this interaction to prevent undesirable consequences.

Abstract

One of the factors capable of improving the competitiveness of enterprises is a factor in innovative development, providing for the interconnected formation of scientific and technical, industrial, financial, social activities in the conditions of a new institutional environment. The large aspect of enterprises is not in the choice of certain directions of innovative management, but in understanding conceptual and methodological approaches to building assessments of the impact of innovative developments and products for competitiveness of firms in order to build an effective innovative enterprise policy.

Regardless of which position, the company is first located, which market share it takes, which is in its size, which is its organizational and legal status, any innovation has been implemented by increasing profits by optimizing production, management systems.

The main objectives of the article is the characteristic of the meaning and features of innovative management into the management of the enterprise and the problems of managing the competitiveness of the enterprise in the criterion of innovative development.

According to the results of the study, it is obvious that in the enterprise, it provides innovative activities, a prerequisite is the constant assessment of the management system of this activity in order to avoid unplanned costs.

Comprehensive monitoring of existing systems in the enterprise will provide him with effective functioning and strong competitive positions. It is found that the company should not be afraid of new changes, and be prepared for innovations, as well as prepare for this personnel. The leaders of enterprises should discuss with their subordinate activities that will occur and give clearly delivered personal tasks.

The inherence to the innovative activity system for such properties as integrity, adaptability, development, compatibility and synergies makes it possible to coach to other management systems in the enterprise. During the operation of systems and their interaction, it is important to monitor this interaction to prevent unwanted consequences.

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